

Development of Textile Reinforcements based on Flax Fibres for Structural Composite Applications

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SUMMARY: The current work aims to develop high-performance natural fibre composite systems for structural applications using continuous textile reinforcements like UD-tapes or woven fabrics. So far, most developments in the area of natural fibre reinforced composites have focused on random discontinuous fibre composite systems based on either non-woven mats or the use of chopped fibres. The development of continuous fibre reinforced composites is however essential for the development of materials which can be used in load-bearing/structural applications. The main problem in this case is the optimisation of the pre-yarn to be used to manufacture the textile reinforcement. Preliminary results on non-crimped unidirectional composites give very promising results since the obtained mechanical properties are higher by a factor of 3 to 4 compared to the current non-woven flax composites.

KEYWORDS: long flax fibres, flax pre-yarns, twist, textile reinforcement

INTRODUCTION

In the last decade research activities in the area of composite materials have shifted towards the development of ‘cost-performance’ engineering materials. Thus, E-glass fibres due to their excellent price-performance ratio are by far the most important fibres for these types of composites. However, these fibres do have some disadvantages regarding (thermal) recycling issues, abrasive wear of processing equipment and are non-renewable. On the other hand, environmental legislation, consumer pressure and waste management are all increasing the pressure to consider the environmental impact of the products at all stages of their life cycle. It is for these reasons that flax fibres are considered as an alternative for glass fibres [1,2].

At this moment natural fibres are pushed due to their ‘green’ image, as mentioned above. They are renewable and can be incinerated at the end of the materials lifetime. However, from an eco-performance point-of-view, mechanical recycling is favoured over thermal recycling and landfill. Thus, problems due to thermal degradation during recycling and reprocessing may significantly lower the eco-performance of natural fibre composites. Hence, for natural fibre composites thermal recycling should be more appropriate, but in this case use of thermoplastic resins (e.g. PP) does not provide any advantage over the use of thermosetting resins [3]. Moreover, thermosetting resins display some advantages over thermoplastic resins, such as: (i) impregnation of fibres is relatively

easy, (ii) relatively simple moulds, (iii) possibility to manufacture large structures in a cost-effective manner and (iv) better mechanical properties.

Currently natural fibre composites are based on short fibres or non-woven needled mats. A clear disadvantage of these randomly oriented, discontinuous flax fibre composites is their low tensile strength (around 50 MPa) compared to glass fibre reinforced composites although they can compete with glass fibre composites (e.g. GMTs) in stiffness (around 5 GPa). Previous studies have shown that similar to the development of advanced composites based on glass or carbon fibres the use of continuous fibre reinforcement is probably the most critical parameter for the improvement of natural fibre composites strength [1]. In the short-fibre composites the reinforcing efficiency of these short fibre systems is fairly limited with the strength of the composite still dominated by the polymer matrix rather than the strong and stiff fibres. It is for this reason that the current work focuses on the development of continuous textile reinforcements like UD tapes or woven fabrics. These reinforcements are used with thermosetting resins (for the reasons mentioned above) in order to develop natural fibre composites for structural applications.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PRE-YARN

It has been shown that unidirectional composites made from long flax fibres (see Fig. 1(a)) in lab scale [4,5] can have sufficiently high mechanical properties, suitable for structural applications. However, if natural fibres are to be used for the production of continuous natural fibre composites on an industrial scale, these discontinuous fibres need to be spun into yarns (see Fig. 1(b)). An important parameter in the development of these yarns is the level of twist. For example, low twisted yarns display a very low strength when tested dry in air and therefore they can not be used in processes such as pultrusion or textile manufacturing routes like knitting or weaving. Hence, these yarns need to have higher levels of twist. On the other hand, when these yarns are impregnated with a polymer resin like epoxy or polyester, the strength of the impregnated yarns may decrease with twist similar to any off-axis composite. In order to investigate the effect of twist, the pre-yarns of Fig. 1(b) were used. For the dry-roving strength, the pre-yarns were manually twisted to different levels of twist and then tested in air in tension at a cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. For the impregnated roving strength, the pre-yarns were first impregnated in an epoxy resin bath and then twisted to different levels. The impregnated rovings were then cured at 60 °C for 16 hrs. The twisting of the pre-yarns after impregnation was chosen in order to exclude the effect of decreasing permeability with increasing twist, allowing in this way to study solely the effect of twist.

The results are given in Fig. 2, where the impregnated and dry roving strength of the pre-yarns of Fig. 1(b) as a function of the twist level are shown. Concerning the dry roving strength it can be observed that at low twist levels e.g. below 29 turns/m the strength is almost zero. As the twist increases the frictional forces between the fibres in the pre-yarn increase since in this case the contact area is higher, which result in a strength increase of the pre-yarn. On the other hand, in the case of impregnated yarns the strength drops gradually with twist. The highest strength is here obtained for yarns with low twist as all fibres are perfectly aligned with the loading direction. With increasing twist the strength drops similar to that of the strength of an off-axis laminate. The critical step in the development of an optimal yarn for composite applications is to find an optimum twist, which results in a minimum loss of properties of the impregnated yarns (read: composites), while maintaining good processability and sufficient strength for textile or composite processes. Clearly, from the results of Fig. 2, a low as possible twist should be preferred, which at the same time displays a sufficiently high strength (of the dry yarns) to fulfil the requirements for a certain manufacturing method.

Fig. 1 (a) hackled long flax fibres, (b) pre-yarn made from long flax fibres. The pre-yarn shown has a twist of 29 turns/m and a tex of 609.

Fig. 2 Strength as a function of the twist level for: ○ impregnated and ■ dry roving (long fibres), respectively. The long fibre rovings have a tex value of 609.

Similar studies were also performed for short fibre yarns (Fig. 3). Here a similar trend is observed as for long flax yarns however the overall properties of the yarns are much lower than those for long fibre yarns, and the strength of the dry yarn is relatively low for many textile operations. From these results it can be seen that long fibre yarns display much better properties than short fibre yarns (600 MPa for impregnated long flax versus 250 MPa for impregnated short fibre yarn). However short fibre rovings are much cheaper than long fibre rovings. It should be noted that zero-twist in the case of short fibre rovings is actually a high level of twist in order to give these short fibre yarns sufficient strength for handling. Therefore the rovings had to be untwisted (negative twist) in order to study the effect of twist over the whole range of twist versus properties. In the case of long flax rovings the as-received rovings had a very low twist level of around 29 turns/m and only a positive twist was applied.

Fig. 3 Strength as a function of the twist level for: ○ impregnated and ■ dry roving (short fibres), respectively. The short fibre rovings have a tex value of 540.

Fig. 4 Hybrid composite tensile strength for different volume fractions of short and long fibre rovings. The overall fibre volume fraction in all cases is about 30%.

Due to the attractive low price of the short fibre yarns compared to long fibre yarns, hybrid composites with an overall fibre volume fraction of 30% were manufactured by mixing short (zero-twist) and long fibre rovings (29 turns/m). This was done to obtain a good balance between cost and performance of the yarns as the addition of cheap short-fibre rovings to the more expensive long-fibre yarns will obviously lower the price. Moreover, the combination of long fibre yarn with short fibre should result in an increase in dry yarn strength as the long fibre yarn can serve as a carrier for the short fibre yarn during textile or composite processing. The unidirectional hybrid composites were prepared using a lab-scale pultrusion process. A polyester resin was used as a matrix material and curing took place at 150 °C for 15 min. Prior to specimen preparation the yarns had been dried at 50 °C for 16 hrs. Two different specimen geometries were employed, a solid circular cross section (diameter of 4 mm) used for tensile tests and rectangular cross section (3 x 4 mm) used for 3-point bending tests. Fig. 4 depicts the hybrid composite strength for different short and long-fibre rovings volume fractions. It can be seen that when only short-fibre rovings are used the tensile strength of the

composites is only ~ 45 MPa. By adding long-fibre rovings and decreasing the amount of short-fibre rovings the tensile strength continuously increases up to ~ 160 MPa when only long-fibre rovings are used. It should be mentioned at this point that in the case of 100% long fibre rovings failure was at the grips, indicating that the actual strength might even be higher. Similar results were obtained for the flexural modulus as can be seen in Fig. 5. In the case of 100% short-fibre rovings the bending stiffness is only ~ 5.5 GPa, while for the case of pure long-fibre rovings the bending stiffness is much higher, approximately 17 GPa. These relatively poor properties for short fibre rovings are not solely the result of the short fibres used but also a result of the relatively high level of twist in short fibre yarn to give it the coherency needed for handling.

Fig. 5 Hybrid composite flexural stiffness for different volume fractions of short and long fibre rovings. The overall fibre volume fraction in all cases is about 30%.

MICROMECHANICS OF YARN COMPOSITES

In order to evaluate the results presented above, some basic micromechanical analysis where performed to get a better insight in the effect of fibre angle (twist) and fibre length (short versus long flax). For this reason the Cox-Krenchel model [6] for composite stiffness was used. The basic assumption made by using this model is to treat the prepared specimens as aligned short fibre composites, where the level of twist determined the off-axis angle of the fibres with respect to the loading axis.

$$E_c = \eta_0 \eta_{LE} V_f E_f + (1 - V_f) E_m \quad \text{Eqn. 1}$$

Where, E_c : composite stiffness

E_f : fibre stiffness

E_m : matrix stiffness

V_f : fibre volume fraction

$\eta_0 = \sum_n \alpha_n \cos^4 \varphi_n$: fibre orientation efficiency factor (related to twist), α_n is the fraction of

fibres with orientation angle φ_n .

$\eta_{LE} = 1 - [\tanh(\beta L / 2) / (\beta L / 2)]$: fibre length efficiency factor (related to fibre length), L is

the fibre length, and $\beta = \frac{2}{D} \left[\frac{2G_m}{E_f \ln(R/r)} \right]^{1/2}$, where D is the fibre diameter, G_m is matrix shear modulus, the factor $\ln(R/r)$ is related to the fibre volume fraction.

As it is known the Cox-Krenchel model requires among others the fibre length as input (see Eqn. 1). For this reason, the fibre length distribution in both short and long fibre yarns was determined. The results are given in Fig. 6 for short fibre yarns and Fig. 7 for long fibre yarns. As expected the average fibre length is much higher in the long fibre yarns (by a factor of 4). In this work a square packed fibre arrangement is assumed, following Thomason and Vluc [7]. In the model a modulus of 50 GPa for the flax fibre and a modulus of 2.5 GPa for the matrix is used. The fibre diameter used is 15 μm . In the calculation of the fibre orientation factor (η_0) it is assumed that all the fibres have the same orientation ($\alpha_n=1$).

Fig. 6 Fibre length distribution in short fibre yarns. The mean value is 17.6 mm and the standard deviation 13.2 mm.

Fig. 7 Fibre length distribution in long fibre yarns. The mean value is 68.4 mm and the standard deviation 37.1 mm.

From the results displayed in Figs 8 and 9 it can be shown that the fibre twist is the most important factor for obtaining high performance composites. The fibre length only affects the composite stiffness at relatively low fibre lengths (approx. 2 mm, which is well below the 17 mm for short fibre rovings used in our study). However in the case of short fibre rovings a high level of twist is required in order to form coherent rovings of reasonable strength and it is this high level of twist and the resulting fibre misalignment, rather than the fibre length, that results in the drop in mechanical properties. This is demonstrated in Fig. 9, where it is shown that only for fibre lengths less than 5 mm there is an effect on the composite modulus. In the case of short fibre rovings the twist angle can be as high as 45° , which means that the theoretical modulus drops from 17 GPa to around 5 GPa, which is similar to experimentally measured values. Similarly, the modulus in the case of pure long-fibre rovings (29 turns/m) is 17 GPa, which is very close to the value predicted from the model when the fibre orientation is 0° . Fig. 10 depicts the model's prediction of the composite stiffness versus the fibre volume fraction, as can be seen for high fibre volume fractions ($>50\%$) the composite stiffness is very high and can easily compete with or out-perform (on a weight basis) glass fibre composites for structural applications.

Fig. 8 Theoretical composite modulus versus fibre length for 5 different fibre orientations. ● UD long fibre yarn / polyester composites, ○ UD of short fibre yarn / polyester composites

Fig. 9 Theoretical composite modulus versus fibre orientation for 5 different fibre lengths.

Fig. 10 Theoretical composite modulus versus the fibre volume fraction.

DEVELOPMENT OF NON-CRIMPED TEXTILE REINFORCEMENT

As it was mentioned above, the developed yarns are to be used in production of composites on an industrial scale. In many composite manufacturing processes such as RTM, spray or hand lay-up, and vacuum infusion the reinforcement is in the form of a fabric. In this section some preliminary results are given concerning the mechanical properties of unidirectional warp-knitted natural fibre composites. In this case the yarns used have a twist of 223 turns/m and a tex value of 210, which is much lower than the tex value of the yarns examined above. As a result of the low tex value these yarns are much finer. Fig. 11(a) displays schematically the mono-axial warp-knitted fabrics manufactures at Eng-Tex (Mullsjö, Sweden) with the flax yarns in the weft direction, and polyester yarns as binder in the warp direction. The mono-axial fabric was also laid up in two layers, with one in the 0° direction and the other in the 90° direction as can be seen in Fig. 11(b).

Fig. 11 a) Mono-axial fabric with 0° fibre direction, b) Two layers of mono-axial fabrics laid in 0° and 90° on top of each other.

The mechanical properties of the unidirectional warp-knitted fabrics by Eng-Tex with polyester and epoxy resin have been evaluated. The specimens were made using hand lay-up in combination with vacuum bagging (during consolidation) and had a fibre volume fraction of 28%. Fig. 12 depicts the longitudinal and transverse strength of the manufactured unidirectional composites.

Fig 12 Mechanical properties of unidirectional warp knitted flax fabrics by Eng-Tex based on epoxy resin and a polyester resin. The fibre volume fraction is 28% in both cases. L= longitudinal direction, and T=transverse direction

Flexural strength values of the knitted fabrics were as high as 160 MPa for the case of polyester resin and 190 MPa for the case of epoxy resin. Despite the relatively low fibre volume fractions because of the hand lay-up method used, these values are already much higher than those of current state of the art non-woven flax fabric based composites which have maximum strengths of around 50 MPa, meaning an increase in strength of some 300-400%. Similarly also the modulus of the current composite (16 GPa) is much higher than those of non-woven flax laminates with typical values of around 4-5Gpa, which is again equivalent to an increase of around 350%.

CONCLUSIONS

From the results presented above it can be concluded that natural fibre composites based on continuous reinforcement present improved properties by a factor of 3 to 4 compared to the current non-woven flax composites and they can even compete fabric based glass-fibre composites in terms of stiffness. A key parameter in the development of these composites is the optimisation of the yarns used to manufacture the reinforcement (e.g. level of twist). Finally, the possibility of mixing long and short-fibre rovings was examined in order to find a good balance between cost and performance of the yarns.

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